

Limiting surface pressures for preloaded bolted connections made of duplex and lean-duplex stainless steel

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ABSTRACT

Bolted connections made of stainless steel are increasingly used as preloaded bolted connections although, besides missing standardised tightening parameters, no regulations regarding preload losses exist so far. Due to this reason, up to now, procedure tests have to be carried out for each specific application and batch of bolting assemblies. This contribution deals with the question of preload losses in stainless steel applications which arise due to the compressive stresses induced under the bolt head and nut or the washers during the tightening process. These stresses might become excessive, can cause time-dependent plastic flow (creep) and may result in high preload losses which have to be for sure avoided in case the preload is used for slip-resistant and/or fatigue loaded connections. To limit the preload losses due to surface pressures, the German guideline VDI 2230-1 provides limiting surface pressures p_G for various kinds of metal materials except for duplex and lean-duplex stainless steels. These values should not be exceeded.

To overcome this lack of knowledge regarding duplex stainless steels, experimental investigations are currently ongoing to determine limiting surface pressures for ease of use in practical design to avoid high preload losses. Furthermore, the question arises whether the limiting surface pressures according to VDI 2230-1 are a meaningful tool to meet the increased safety requirements in civil engineering structures or whether higher requirements have to be defined. This contribution aims to give an overview of limiting surface pressures for preloaded bolted connections made of duplex and lean-duplex steel.

Keywords: bolted connections, limiting surface pressure, duplex stainless steel, lean-duplex stainless steel

1 INTRODUCTION

In steel construction, bolted connections and structures made of stainless steel have been increasingly used as load-bearing components, for example in bridges, gantries, expansion joints, facades and coastal protection structures (1, 2). Stainless steel is used because of its high ductility, excellent durability, work hardening effects and high resistance against corrosion even in aggressive environments compared to corrosion-prone carbon steel (1, 2).

Preloaded bolted connections (e. g. category E according to EN 1993-1-8 (3)) generate compressive stresses under the bolt head and nut or the washers on the clamping package due to the preloading process. However, excessive compressive stresses can cause time-dependent plastic flow (creep), which may result in high preload losses in a preloaded bolted connection. Therefore, preloaded bolted connections made of stainless steel are currently normative not permitted due to the lack of knowledge regarding the loss of preload which is caused by the viscoplastic deformation behaviour and the missing normative regulations in civil engineering. Due to this reason, up to now, procedure tests have to be carried out for each specific application. On the other hand, in mechanical engineering limiting surface pressures are used according to German guideline VDI 2230-1 (4) to limit time-dependent plastic flow and preload losses of preloaded bolted connections.

VDI 2230-1 defines limiting surface pressures p_G , which shall not be exceeded to avoid high preload losses and plastic flow (creep). For duplex and lean-duplex stainless steel, the limiting surface pressures are missing. Furthermore, the question arises whether the limiting surface pressures according to VDI 2230-1 are meaningful to meet the increased safety requirements in civil engineering structures.

Therefore, systematic experimental and numerical investigations are currently conducted in the frame of the research project „Preloaded bolted connections made of stainless steel under fatigue loading in civil engineering structures” funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) – 521501197 at the Institute for Metal and Lightweight Structures (IML) of the University of Duisburg-Essen (UDE), Germany. In this paper, an overview of the experimental investigations into limiting surface pressures for preloaded bolted connections made of duplex and lean-duplex stainless steel is given.

2 GENERAL OVERVIEW

2.1 General

In order to be able to use stainless steel bolts in cyclic loading structures, the bolting assemblies must be preloaded to prevent premature failure of the bolts. Preloaded bolted connections made of stainless steel are currently normative not permitted due to concerns about cold welding effects due to the preloading process (“galling”) and regarding the loss of preload as a result of the viscoplastic deformation behaviour (creep and relaxation) of the components. For this reason, so far, no stainless steel bolting assemblies for preloading have been developed in accordance with EN 14399-1 (5) for carbon steel. Furthermore, no generalized tightening parameters have been worked out for bolts according to e.g. EN ISO 4014/4017 (6,7) currently available on the market for non-preloaded connections. However, it could be shown that non-preloaded bolting assemblies according to EN 15048-1 (8) made of stainless steel can be used for preloading guaranteeing a secure tightening in principle (9-13). For this reason, a “Bolt Tightening Qualification Procedure” (BTQP) (14-17) was developed to specify a qualification procedure for the use of preloaded bolting assemblies made of stainless steel.

In addition to the reservations about the viscoplastic deformation behaviour and the tightening behaviour, the actual fatigue behaviour of bolts made of stainless steel is nearly unknown with the exception of some publications (18-20). As already mentioned, bolted connections must be preloaded to prevent premature failure in cyclic loaded structures. Thereby, the questions arise, whether the FAT classes according to EN 1993-1-9 (21) historically developed for bolts made of carbon steel can be safely applied to stainless steel bolts due to their different material behaviour. Therefore, experimental investigations into the fatigue behaviour of bolts made of stainless steel considering the vast variety of stainless steel grades, different property classes, bolt diameters and bolt types are currently conducted at UDE-IML, which will be presented in a future publication.

Fig. 1. Exemplary surface pressures under the washer of a preloaded bolted connection

To avoid plastic flow (creep) and high preload losses, the German guideline VDI 2230-1 defines limiting surface pressures p_G for the assembly and the working state for different materials. These

limiting surface pressures shall limit the plastic deformations under the head and under the nut or under the washers of the components, see Fig. 1. However, as already mentioned, values for limiting surface pressures for duplex and lean-duplex-steel are missing. Furthermore, the question arises as the limiting surface pressures defined in the German guideline VDI 2230-1 developed for mechanical engineering can be transferred to the increased safety requirements in civil engineering according to the Eurocode.

2.2 Determining the surface pressure p_{\max} according to VDI 2230-1

In the contact surfaces between the bolt head and nut on the one hand and the clamped package on the other hand, according to the German guideline VDI 2230-1, defined surface pressures p_{\max} should not be exceeded during the assembly state ($p_{M,\max}$) and working state ($p_{B,\max}$), see Eq. (1) and (2). The limit value represents the limiting surface pressure p_G , which is the maximum permissible pressure under the bolt head, nut or washers of the clamped material. Time-dependent plastic flow which may result in loss of preload should not become effective if the limiting surface pressure is maintained either as a result of assembly preload or the maximum load in service and working state.

$$\text{Assembly state: } p_{M,\max} = F_{M,\text{zul}} / A_{p,\min} \leq p_G \quad (1)$$

$$\text{working state: } p_{B,\max} = (F_{V,\max} + F_{SA,\max} - \Delta F_{V,\text{th}}) / A_{p,\min} \leq p_G \quad (2)$$

where $F_{M,\text{zul}}$ permissible assembly preload,
 $A_{p,\min}$ minimum bearing area of the bolt head or nut,
 $F_{V,\max}$ maximum preload,
 $F_{SA,\max}$ maximum of the additional axial bolt load and
 $\Delta F_{V,\text{th}}$ the additional thermal load.

Experimentally determined values of limiting surface pressures p_G are given in Table A9 of VDI 2230-1. The experimental determination of limiting surface pressures can be carried out either by discontinuous pressure tests according to Hasselmann (22) or by continuous pressure tests according to Arz et al. (23). Anyway, for those materials for which the limiting surface pressure has not yet been determined acc. to (22) or (23), VDI 2230-1 states that it can be set as $p_G = 3 \text{ HB}$ (Brinell hardness). It should be noted that all values of the given limiting surface pressures in VDI 2230-1 are short-term values at room temperature. Furthermore, the limiting surface pressure for austenitic stainless steel (1.4401) according to VDI 2230-1 is not verified according to the procedures of Hasselmann (22) or Arz et al. (23) and values for duplex- and lean-duplex-steel are missing as already mentioned.

2.3 Literature review

The literature contains a large number of experimental studies into the determination of limiting surface pressures of various materials at room temperature (22-30) and elevated temperature (31, 32). The continuous pressure tests of Arz et al. (23) relying on a plastic deformation of $20 \mu\text{m}$ are recommended by Stolle/Berger (26) as a method for the consistent database and are therefore used in the following. Furthermore, investigations of Hasselmann (22) and Stolle/Berger (26) have shown that there is a positive effect on the limiting surface pressures due to the supporting effect of chamfers in the through-hole. In addition, Oechsner et al. (30) investigated different surface roughnesses of specimens (machining or machining with polishing), but no significant influence on the expected limiting surface pressures could be determined. As already mentioned, experimental investigations into limiting surface pressures of duplex and lean-duplex steel are not available in literature.

3 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

3.1 General

In order to carry out an experimental determination of the limiting surface pressure p_G according to VDI 2230-1 (4) for duplex (1.4462), lean-duplex stainless steel (1.4162), and as a comparison for structural steel S355J2+N (1.0577), continuous pressure tests were carried out. For each material,

five pressure tests on specimens without chamfers and three pressure tests on specimens with chamfers were performed.

3.2 Test programme

The continuous pressure tests were performed according to Arz et al. (23) at the Institute for Metal and Lightweight Structures of the University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany. The test rig is shown in Fig. 2a).

Fig. 2. a) Test rig for the compression tests, b) schematic view of a test sample and c) specimens with and without chamfer

The specimens had an outer diameter of $d_a = 20$ mm, a height of $h = 10$ mm, an inner diameter for the specimens without/with chamfer on the upper surface of $d_h = 10.5$ mm/ $d_{ha} = 11.5$ mm, see Fig. 2b) and c). The test material was taken from sheet material in thickness direction from the upper edge of the sheet. The specimens were produced by machining. Furthermore, the upper surfaces of the specimens without chamfer but with a removed burr were additionally machined and had a surface roughness of $R_z = 3-7$ μm , see Fig. 2c) left. The surfaces of the specimens with chamfer had a surface roughness of $R_z = 11-38$ μm , see Fig. 2c) right. The material properties of the stainless steel sheet material were determined in rolling direction and perpendicular to the rolling direction already by Stranghöner/Abraham (33) by tensile tests according to EN ISO 6892-1 (34). The material properties of the carbon steel sheet were taken from the inspection test certificate 3.1 according to EN 10204 (35).

The load was applied using a hardened compression die (> 60 HRC). The outer diameter of the compression die was $d_w = 14.6$ mm and was defined by Arz et al. (23) based on the flat head contact surface of an M10 bolt head according to EN ISO 4014/4017. In addition, a hardened connection (> 60 HRC) was arranged between the ring specimen and the adaption to the testing machine. The hardness of the test apparatuses should ensure that only the sample exhibits plastic deformation. The plastic deformations were measured using a high-resolution displacement transducer. Furthermore, the geometry of the specimen (h , d_h or d_{ha}) and the compression die (d_w and the inner diameter or the compression die d_{wi}) was determined at several measuring points using calibrated calliper before the tests to achieve the actual contact surfaces for the test evaluation.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

4.1 Material properties

The results of the tension tests for determining the material properties of the yield strength $R_{p0.2}$, the tensile strength R_m and the elongation after fracture A are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Material properties of the sheet material used for the compression tests

Material Name / Material Number	Yield Strength	Tensile Strength	Elongation after Fracture
	$R_{p0,2}$ [N/mm ²]	R_m [N/mm ²]	A [%]
Duplex / 1.4462	590 / 560 ²⁾	796 / 766 ²⁾	33,1 / 36,4 ²⁾
Lean-Duplex / 1.4162	549 / 507 ²⁾	717 / 712 ²⁾	35,2 / 41,3 ²⁾
S355J2+N / 1.0577	479 ¹⁾	573 ¹⁾	23,7

¹⁾ According to inspection test certificate 3.1 acc. to EN 10204 | ²⁾ In rolling direction / perpendicular to the rolling direction from (33)

The requirements according to EN 10088-2 (36) and EN 10025-2 (37) for the sheet material were achieved for the yield and tensile strength as well as for the elongation after fracture.

4.2 Limiting surface pressures of duplex and lean-duplex stainless steel

In total, 21 continuous compression tests were carried out for the determination of the limiting surface pressures. According to VDI 2230-1, a plastic deformation of 20 μm and the corresponding stress $p_{0.2\%} = p_G$ were applied. The plastic deformation of 20 μm was defined by Arz et al. (23) on the basis of the 0.2 % compression limit according to DIN 50106 (38) for a specimen height of $h = 10 \text{ mm}$. To evaluate the limiting surface pressures of the tested materials, a straight line was set in the elastic region of the load-deformation curve, and offsetted again by a plastic deformation of 5 μm , 10 μm , 20 μm , and 100 μm . The point of intersection between the load-deformation curve and the offset lines was analysed. After determining the resulting force for the different values of deformation, the actual measured contact area was used as the basis for the evaluation of the surface pressures. Table 2 summarizes the surface pressures $p_{0.05\%} = p_{5 \mu\text{m}}$, $p_{0.1\%} = p_{10 \mu\text{m}}$, $p_{0.2\%} = p_{20 \mu\text{m}} = p_{G,MV}$, and $p_{1\%} = p_{100 \mu\text{m}}$ of the tested specimens without chamfer including the coefficient of variations (COV).

Table 2. Summary of the experimental mean limiting surface pressures of specimens without chamfer

Material Name / Material Number	Surface Pressure ¹⁾							
	$p_{5 \mu\text{m}}$ [N/mm ²]	COV [%]	$p_{10 \mu\text{m}}$ [N/mm ²]	COV [%]	$p_{20 \mu\text{m}} = p_{G,MV}$ [N/mm ²]	COV [%]	$p_{100 \mu\text{m}}$ [N/mm ²]	COV [%]
Duplex / 1.4462	982	2.3	1040	2.1	1109	1.8	1348	1.9
Lean-Duplex / 1.4162	914	2.2	966	1.5	1028	1.6	1237	1.6
S355J2+N / 1.0577	664	7.3	712	5.6	768	4.3	994	1.4

¹⁾ Mean value from $n = 5$ specimens without chamfer

The tests on structural steel S355J2+N verify the suitability of the test apparatus resulted in experimental limiting surface pressures of $p_{G,mv,1.0577} = 768 \text{ N/mm}^2$ which is comparable to the limiting surface pressure given in VDI 2230-1 for S355J0 with $p_G = 760 \text{ N/mm}^2$. The experimentally determined limiting surface pressures for duplex stainless steel (1.4462) becomes $p_{G,mv,1.4462} = 1109 \text{ N/mm}^2$ and for lean-duplex stainless steel (1.4162) $p_{G,mv,1.4162} = 1028 \text{ N/mm}^2$. The COV of the limiting surface pressures for duplex and lean-duplex are even significantly lower than the COV for structural steel. Exemplary, the plastic deformation after the continuous pressure test is shown in Fig. 3a) for a specimen made of lean duplex steel without chamfer.

The results of the surface pressures of the tested specimens without chamfer $p_{20 \mu\text{m}} = p_{G,MV}$ and with chamfer $p_{20 \mu\text{m}} = p_{G,WC}$ are summarised in Table 3 including the coefficient of variations (COV).

The experimentally determined limiting surface pressure for specimens with chamfer made of duplex stainless steel (1.4462) becomes $p_{G,WC,1.4462} = 1171 \text{ N/mm}^2$ and for lean-duplex stainless steel (1.4162) it yields to $p_{G,WC,1.4162} = 1097 \text{ N/mm}^2$. The experimentally determined limiting surface pressures for duplex and lean-duplex stainless steel specimens with chamfer show a minor increase in the limiting surface pressure of 6 % respectively 7 % compared to that achieved for duplex and lean-duplex stainless steel specimens without chamfer. This observation can be attributed to the supporting effect of the chamfer (26). Exemplary, the plastic deformation after the continuous pressure test is shown in Fig. 3b) for a specimen made of lean duplex stainless steel with chamfer.

Table 3. Comparison of the experimental mean limiting surface pressures of the specimens without and with chamfer

Material Name / Material Number	Surface Pressure without Chamfer ¹⁾			Surface Pressure with Chamfer ²⁾			Comparison $p_{G,WC} / p_{G,MV}$
	$Rz_{mean}^{3)}$ [μm]	$p_{20 \mu m} = p_{G,MV}$ [N/mm^2]	COV [%]	$Rz_{mean}^{3)}$ [μm]	$p_{20 \mu m} = p_{G,WC}$ [N/mm^2]	COV [%]	
Duplex / 1.4462	3	1109	1.8	32	1171	1.5	1.06
Lean-Duplex / 1.4162	3	1028	1.6	38	1097	0.6	1.07
S355J2+N / 1.0577	7	768	4.3	11	690	1.9	0.90

¹⁾ Mean value from n = 5 specimens without chamfer | ²⁾ Mean value from n = 3 specimens with chamfer | ³⁾ Surface roughness acc. to EN ISO 21920-2 (39)

The tests on the specimens with chamfer made of S355J2+N resulted in experimental limiting surface pressures of $p_{G,WC,1.0577} = 690 \text{ N/mm}^2$. The limiting surface pressure for S355J2+N determined for specimens with chamfer is reduced compared to the interfacial pressure determined on samples without chamfer. This result is surprising and will be further investigated in future, as, acc. to VDI 2230, the presence of a chamfer might lead to an increase of p_G up to 25 % and not to a decrease.

The influence of different surface conditions (polishing and machining) of the specimens on the limiting surface pressures was already investigated by Oechsner et al. (30) resulting into the conclusion that no influence could be observed. However, the surface roughness of the specimens in the presented tests at UDE (machining up to $Rz_{mean} = 7 \mu m$ and delivery state $Rz_{mean} = 38 \mu m$) was higher than the surface roughness investigated in (30) (machining with polishing up to $Rz_{target} = 0.3 \mu m$ and machining $Rz_{max} = 20 \mu m$). For this reason, in future, further investigations will be carried out into the influence of the surface roughness, also to determine the long-term properties of the tested materials.

Fig. 3. Exemplary sample surface after continuous compression test a) for a specimen with and b) without chamfer made of lean-duplex stainless steel

4.3 Discussion

In order to provide an overview of the surface pressures of preloaded bolted connections made of stainless steel, the surface pressure resulting from preloading of bolts according to EN ISO 4014/4017 of property classes (PC) 80 and 100 in combination with nuts according to EN ISO 4032 (40) and washers according to EN ISO 7089 (41) were calculated by Stranghöner et al. (12, 13) for the preload levels of $F_{p,C}$ (Eq. (3)) according to EN 1090-2 (42) and EN 1993-1-8 as well as $F_{p,C}^*$ (Eq. (4)) according to German DAST-Guideline 024 (43). Since no stainless steel bolting assemblies made of stainless steel have been developed so far for preloading in accordance with EN 14399-1, the preload levels are used as a basis for comparison in the following. For the calculation of $F_{p,C}^*$, the nominal values of proof stresses at the 0.2% non-proportional elongation of stainless steel bolts according to EN ISO 3506-1 (44) are used. The nominal values of proof stresses at the 0.2% non-proportional elongation of stainless steel bolts of PC 80 and 100 are lower than the yield strength of carbon steel bolts of PC 8.8 and 10.9.

$$F_{p,C} = 0.7 \cdot f_{ub} \cdot A_s \quad (3)$$

$$F_{p,C}^* = 0.7 \cdot f_{yb} \cdot A_s \quad (4)$$

where $F_{p,C}$ preload level acc. to EN 1090-2 and EN 1993-1-8,
 $F_{p,C}^*$ preload level acc. to German DAST-Guideline 024,
 f_{ub} tensile strength (R_{mf}) of the bolt acc. to EN ISO 3506-1,
 f_{yb} proof stress at 0.2 % non-proportional elongation (R_{pf}) of the bolt acc. to EN ISO 3506-1,
 A_s tensile stress area of the bolt acc. to EN ISO 3506-1.

A comparison of the resulting calculated surface pressures of preloaded bolted assemblies according to EN ISO 4014/4017/4032/7089 for the preload levels of $F_{p,C}$ and $F_{p,C}^*$ (nominal proof strength f_y for S355, 1.4301, 1.4162 and 1.4462 according to EN 1993-1-8 and EN 1993-1-4 (45)) are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Comparison of the surface pressures under the washer for the nominal yield strength f_y for S355, 1.4301, 1.4162 and 1.4462 (12, 13)

Preloading of stainless steel bolts ISO 4014/4017, PC 80 to preload level $F_{p,C}^*$ results in maximum surface pressures up to ca. 215 N/mm^2 and minimum surface stresses of ca. 140 N/mm^2 , see Fig. 4, which can be categorised as uncritical as their maximum value lies at the nominal proof strength of an austenitic stainless steel 1.4301.

Preloading of stainless steel bolts ISO 4014/4017, PC 100 up to preload levels of $F_{p,C}$ and $F_{p,C}^*$ results in maximum surface pressures of about 355 N/mm^2 and minimum surface pressures of about 190 N/mm^2 , see Fig. 4. These surface pressures are well below the nominal proof strength of duplex stainless steel (1.4462) with $f_y = 460 N/mm^2$ and lean-duplex stainless steel (1.4162) with $f_y = 450 N/mm^2$ and far below the experimentally determined limiting surface pressures of duplex (1.4462) $p_{G,mv,1.4462} = 1109 N/mm^2$ and lean-duplex (1.4162) $p_{G,mv,1.4162} = 1028 N/mm^2$ for a plastic deformation of 20 μm . With these surface pressures, only elastic deformations can be expected. Looking at the experimentally determined stress-deformation curves, exemplary given in Fig. 5 for duplex stainless steel 1.4462, it becomes obvious that at a surface pressure of about 355 N/mm^2 , an elastic deformation of about 38 μm (33.5-39 μm over all tests) results. For lean-duplex stainless steel, the elastic deformations at a surface pressure of about 355 N/mm^2 were in the same range of about 34.5-39 μm .

Fig. 5. Exemplary stress-deformation curve of test specimen 01 without chamfer, duplex stainless steel 1.4462

Therefore, there are no objections by preloading stainless steel bolting assemblies on duplex (1.4462) and lean-duplex (1.4162) stainless steel regarding the surface pressures.

Nevertheless, the surface pressures for ISO 4014/4017 bolts, PC 100 preloaded to $F_{p,C}$ and $F_{p,C}^*$, see Fig. 4, are far above the nominal yield strength f_y of austenitic stainless steel (1.4301) of $f_y = 210 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for nearly all bolt diameters. Herewith, it is highly recommended to experimentally determine also the limiting surface pressure for austenitic stainless steel in order to verify the only “estimated” value given in VDI 2230-1. Nevertheless, it becomes obvious that surface pressures above the proof strength of a material used for a clamped package might lead to severe plastic deformations which should be avoided – at least in civil engineering structures – this is part of future investigations discussing whether the given limiting surface pressures for mechanical engineering structures on the basis of $20 \mu\text{m}$ plastic deformation according to VDI 2230-1 can be applied as well to civil engineering structures. For this reason, further experimental and numerical investigations into the load-bearing behaviour of preloaded bolted connections made of stainless steel are currently conducted.

5 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The aim of this contribution was to determine limiting surface pressures according to VDI 2230-1 made of duplex and lean-duplex stainless steel and to discuss to what extent limiting surface pressures are a useful tool to meet the increased safety requirements in civil engineering structures.

In the frame of the presented investigations, limiting surface pressures for duplex (1.4462) and lean-duplex (1.4162) stainless steel could be determined to $p_{G,mv,1.4462} = 1109 \text{ N/mm}^2$ and $p_{G,mv,1.4162} = 1028 \text{ N/mm}^2$. Preloading of stainless steel bolts ISO 4014/4017, PC 100 up to the preload level $F_{p,C}$ results in maximum surface pressures of about 355 N/mm^2 . Hence, elastic deformations of about $33.5\text{-}39 \mu\text{m}$ for duplex and $34.5\text{-}39 \mu\text{m}$ for lean-duplex stainless steel have to be expected.

In future, further investigations will be carried out to determine the limiting surface pressures of other duplex (1.4410) and lean-duplex (1.4362) materials as well as the expected preload losses (long-term properties). An assessment to what extent the limiting surface pressures for mechanical engineering structures on the basis of $20 \mu\text{m}$ plastic deformation according to VDI 2230-1 can be transferred to civil engineering structures can only be made considering future results to be conducted in the course of the ongoing research project considering e. g. also effects of the surface roughness.

Finally, the load-bearing behaviour during tightening, the viscoplastic deformation behaviour and the fatigue behaviour of preloaded bolted connections made of stainless steel will be investigated. The objective will be to define boundary conditions for the use of stainless steel bolts acc. to EN ISO 4014/4017 in preloaded connections as well as to develop an optimised type of bolting assemblies for preloading made of stainless steel for use in civil engineering.

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REFERENCES

1. **Stranghöner, N., Baddoo, N., Meza, F., Ulbrich, D., Abraham, C., Jungbluth, D.** Neue Entwicklungen in prEN 1993-1-4:2022. Stahlbau Kalender 2023, pp. 299-390, Ernst & Sohn GmbH & Co. KG, Berlin.
2. **Stranghöner, N., Baddoo, N., Stehr, S.** Nichtrostender Stahl im Bauwesen - Bemessung von Stahltagwerken aus nichtrostendem Stahl nach DIN EN 1993-1-4. Stahlbau 87, H. 3, pp. 279-283, 2018.

3. **EN 1993-1-8:2010-12**, Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures – Part 1-8: Design of joints (EN 1993-1-8:2005 + AC:2009).
4. **VDI 2230-1:2015-11**, Systematic calculation of highly stressed bolted joints - Joints with one cylindrical bolt. Beuth Verlag GmbH, Berlin.
5. **EN 14399-1:2015-04**, High-strength structural bolting assemblies for preloading –Part 1: General requirements (EN 14399-1:2015).
6. **EN ISO 4014:2022-10**, Fasteners – Hexagon head bolts – Product grades A and B (EN ISO 4014:2022).
7. **EN ISO 4017:2022-10**, Fasteners – Hexagon head screws – Product grades A and B (EN ISO 4017:2022).
8. **EN 15048-1:2016-09**, Non-preloaded structural bolting assemblies – Part 1: General requirements (EN 15048-1:2016).
9. **Stranghöner, N., Afzali, N., Jungbluth, D., Abraham, C., Veljkovic, M., Bijlaard, F., Gresnigt, N., de Vries, P., Kolstein, H., Nijgh, M., Schedin, E., Pilhagen, J., Jakobsen, E., Söderman, A., Glienke, R., Ebert, A., Baddoo, N., Chen, A., Hradil, P., Talja, A., Rantala, J., Auerkari, P., Säynäjäkangas, J., Manninen, T., Rudolf, A., Berger, S., Cook, M., Taylor, M., Huckshold, M.** Execution and reliability of slip-resistant connections for steel structures using CS and SS, Res Progr of the Research Fund for Coal a. Steel, RFSR-CT-2014-00024, Final Report, 2018.
10. **Stranghöner, N., Abraham, C., Afzali, N., Jungbluth, D.** Preloading behaviour and preloading levels for stainless steel bolt assemblies including relaxation with detailed specifications for recommended preloading levels, RFCS research project SIROCO (RFSR-CT-2014-00024), Deliverable report D5.4. 30 March 2018.
11. **Stranghöner, N., Jungbluth, D., Afzali, N., Abraham, C.** Vorgespannte Schraubverbindungen aus nichtrostendem Stahl, Stahlbau 89, No. 4, 2020 pp. 326-338
12. **Stranghöner, N., Jungbluth, D., Afzali, N., Lorenz, C.** Einblick in das Vorspannverhalten von geschraubten Verbindungen aus nichtrostendem Stahl, Stahlbau 86, No. 4, 2017, pp. 302-314.
13. **Stranghöner, N., Jungbluth, D., Abraham, C., Söderman, A.** Tightening behaviour of preloaded stainless steel bolting assemblies, Steel Construction 10, No. 4, 2017, pp. 319-332.
14. **Stranghöner, N., Jungbluth, D.** Verfahrensprüfung zur Bestimmung von Anziehparametern für vorgespannte geschraubte Verbindungen, Stahlbau 86, No. 12, 2017, pp. 1079-1088.
15. **Stranghöner, N., Jungbluth, D., Abraham, C.** Guidance for Preloading of Stainless Steel Bolting Assemblies using a Bolt Tightening Qualification Procedure, Proceedings of Nordic Steel 2019 Conference, Copenhagen, Denmark, No. 3-4, pp. 919–924.
16. **Jungbluth, D., Stranghöner, N., Afzali, N., Abraham, C.** Bolt Tightening Qualification Procedure (BTQP) for Preloaded Bolted Connections Made of Stainless Steel, 29th International Society of Offshore and Polar Engineers Conference, ISOPE, Honolulu, USA, 16-21 June 2019.
17. **Jungbluth, D., Abraham, C., Lorenz, C., Stranghöner, N.** Newest findings in preloading of stainless steel bolting assemblies, Stainless Steel in Structures-Sixth International Experts Seminar, 20-21 Sept. 2022, London, UK.
18. **Wang, J., Brian, U., Li, D., Song, Y.** Fatigue behaviour of stainless steel bolts in tension and shear under constant-amplitude loading, International Journal of Fatigue 133, 2020, 105401.
19. **Hechler, O.** Über das Ermüdungsverhalten von Konstruktionen aus Duplex-Stahl, Dissertation, 2008, Aachen.
20. **Stranghöner, N., Ehrhardt, L.** Fatigue resistance of austenitic stainless steel bolts under tension, Proceedings of Eurosteel 2023 Conference, Amsterdam, Netherlands, ce/papers 6 (2023), Issue 3-4, p. 2423-2428, 12-14 September 2023.
21. **EN 1993-1-9:2010-12**, Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures – Part 1-9: Fatigue (EN 1993-1-9:2005 + AC:2009).
22. **Hasselmann, U.** Grenzflächenpressung verspannter Teile – Geometrieabhängige Werkstoffkennwerte zur Berechnung von Schraubenverbindungen, 5. Informationsveranstaltung Schraubenverbindungen – Neue Ergebnisse aus Forschung und Praxis, 1997, Darmstadt.

23. **Arz, U., Berger, C., Müller, H., Westphal, K.** Surface-pressure of clamped materials, *Konstruktion* 54, Heft 7/8, S. 38-42, 2002.
24. **Hamm, B.** Schraubenverbindungen im Leichtbau, *VDI-Z.* 99, Issue 3, pp. 10-104, 1957.
25. **Junker, G. H.** Flächenpressungen unter Schraubenköpfen, *Maschinenmarkt (Sonderdruck)*, 1961, Nr. 38, pp. 1-7.
26. **Stolle, C., Berger, C.** Einflüsse auf die Veränderung der Vorspannkraft unter Betriebsbedingungen bei Verschraubungen im modernen Leichtbau, Final report, IGF-No. 13639 N, Technical University of Darmstadt, Center for Structural Materials, 2005, Darmstadt, Germany.
27. **Stolle, C., Berger, C., Arz, U.** Limiting Surface Pressure of Modern Materials, Deutscher Schraubenverband (DSV), 2006, Darmstadt, Germany.
28. **Stolle, C., Berger, C., Arz, U.** Limiting Surface Pressure – Startin of Permanent On-Site Deformation of Mordern Materials, *Konstruktion*, Issue 5, pp. 77-82, 2006.
29. **Arz, U., Baumgart, H., Kremer, U., Marx, T., Stolle, C.** Limiting surface pressure under continued pressure of ferrous and lightweight metals, *Materials Science & Engineering Technology* 37, Issue 10, pp. 894-899.
30. **Oechsner, M., Kempf, A., Friedrich, C., Peth, J.** Rechnerische Beschreibung des Relaxationsverhaltens von Schraubenverbindungen unter leichtbaurelevanten Temperaturbelastung, Final report, IGF-No. 18670 N, Technical University of Darmstadt, Center for Structural Materials, Chair of Machine Elements, Fastening Systems and Product Innovation, University of Siegen, 2018, Darmstadt/Siegen, Germany.
31. **Arz, U., Berger, C., Kaiser, U., Kremer, U.** Grenzflächenpressung von Leichtmetallen unter kontinuierlicher Beanspruchung bei Temperaturen bis 150 °C, *Konstruktion*, 03/2003, pp. 63-67.
32. **Kempf, A., Klein, M., Oechsner, M.** Determination of the limiting surface pressure of component materials used in bolted joints on ring-shaped specimens at elevated temperature up to 300 °C, *Forschung im Ingenieurwesen* 84, pp. 379-386, 2020.
33. **Stranghöner, N., Abraham, C.** Development of normative principles regarding the load bearing capacity of bolted connections loaded in shear and tension made of austenitic and austenitic-ferritic (duplex) stainless steel M12 to M36, Final report of research project P 1386, IGF-No. 20651 N, University of Duisburg-Essen, Institute for Metal and Lightweight Structures, 2021, Essen, Germany.
34. **EN ISO 6892-1:2017-02**, Metallic materials – Tensile testing – Part 1: Method of test at room temperature (ISO 6892-1:2016).
35. **EN 10204:2005-01**, Metallic products - Types of inspection documents (EN 10204:2004).
36. **EN 10088-2:2014-12**, Stainless steels - Part 2: Technical delivery conditions for sheet/plate and strip of corrosion resisting steels for general purposes.
37. **EN 10025-2:2019-10**, Hot rolled products of structural steels - Part 2: Technical delivery conditions for non-alloy structural steels.
38. **DIN 50106:2023-02**, Testing of metallic materials - Compression test at room temperature.
39. **EN ISO 21920-2:2022-12**, Geometrical product specifications (GPS) - Surface texture: Profile - Part 2: Terms, definitions and surface texture parameters (ISO 21920-2:2021).
40. **EN ISO 4032:2013-04**, Hexagon regular nuts (style 1) – Product grades A and B (EN ISO 4032:2012).
41. **EN ISO 7089:2000-11**, Plain washers – Normal series, Product grade A (EN ISO 7089:2000).
42. **EN 1090-2:2018-09**, Execution of steel structures and aluminium structure –Part 2: Technical requirements for steel structures.
43. **DASt-Richtlinie 024:2018-06**, Anziehen von geschraubten Verbindungen der Abmessung M12 bis M36.
44. **EN ISO 3506-1:2020-08**, Fasteners - Mechanical properties of corrosion-resistant stainless steel fasteners – Part 1: Bolts, screws and studs with specified grades and property classes (EN ISO 3506-1:2020).
45. **EN 1993-1-4:2015-10**, Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures – Part 1-4: General rules – Supplementary rules for stainless steel (EN 1993-1-4:2006 + A1:2015).